

Supplementary Material 4

Amino acid sequences of known regulators of shape in tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*), and predicted genes in carrot (*Daucus carota* var. *sativus*) with sequence homology to the shape regulon *OFP-TRM* and IQD. Assembly, GCA_001625215.1, bioproject PRJNA268187

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Carrot Tonnu Recruiting motif (TRM) amino acid sequences with homology to tomato TRMs.

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>DCAR_020774 (DCARv2_Chr6:28467368..28472283)
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PCNVEKVPGHMKRLVFDLITEEKNGMDNRDDAMVKLVCKRLGSWKEVESNTIDMMVELDLK
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>DCAR_025439 (DCARv2_Chr7:27232257..27236706)
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VSASQSRSNYQPIERGTENGISRQTTSLNQEPGSNKRPSAIVARLMGLEPTPDESQSLLEDKES
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>DCAR_025910 (DCARv2_Chr7:31634058..31637198)
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STNYTSVHQHQDGLIELLCNKPQVLEPYHPTISLSE
GRPGLPLVTDVFS DASELLSRVGNIGSRLGGTELDYAKEVILNAELLLGSSVQRDNDMNKGFVS
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CII EYLD SRYGPHLRYKNKTPRNLPSCINAEVLINEIVKEIMSWKALASLIPDGHIEKEMSSFLDRS
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>DCAR_024016 (DCARv2_Chr7:7948275..7949513)
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>DCAR_027681 (DACRv2_Chr8:20635645..20639639)
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>DCAR_028703 (DCARv2_Chr8:2501854..2504094)
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GCMTLEEI IQNMQFKGLLDRNQFQIYDSSSESEDQLRNHAPPVVMKPVHAGDGANDFFSRKCI
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SVRS SHEHLSSPAMKLRKSETGPSIHERKLTTQQNS
TKSKLINKALASNFKNGLKPTITSTNNLQDPSIVHKGKEAHTDQRKKADPNVKD TTATPQLRAEE
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>DCAR_029362 (DCARv2_Chr9:5391980..5397183)
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>DCAR_030482 (DCARv2_Chr9:25854383..25828162)
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SKFSWAEDSKRNGMDVISFTFTAPMGRSLPVPETSRDVLKNNAFSADFEGKKVFFNSGGTN
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KHANIAVIDAVRPVKWELEYVKTILCNTETMFKDVS
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>DCAR_000349 (DCARv2_C10729808:1394..3970)
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NSIVLLKPRQTKHERDIFRKHRLNLESSNRATGGKHLHLPTVSSFNQRDIEAKKHLSEMLRNAEN
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GMDASVCPQRIQFSSCSNYEFARDDNSSPLQNSEVAASSTLMKLTGDSPIVRFTKEITEPVYSS
DGLSYEAYANDMEMNDTIISEGLDISEAACAEQSST
FFECPIQDFWLENKPLNSSSVFSSNPWTEREEHPSNSVLEALFTKDFTGLSSNTNCSAISHT
RPHHTDGKEASLVKDHIRNLLQTTELHWEELSKKSH
PSIQLLNISLVEHTLFLDFIKDILLELHQCHFDFYPRVPSIRQNTLASLVLAKNMMEEFMEEIQW
YLVPPAMPRTLEDLAIKDTKKDEIWSGRKLETEE
VVTQLTDCMLEELIMQTTYVGEK

Carrot Ovate family proteins (OFPs) amino acid sequences with homology to tomato OFPs.

>DCAR_008765 (DCARv2_Chr3:1037958..1038569)
MPVSFNTQHCPSPSQKIYNPVAFGSDDSAWPITPPPKGGNSKPQRINNKNKSKVSSVSSGE
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FGNVSISSEKFGTSSKKNNDRNGGNEVVKKSSTSVFKRLMTSCAVNDESAVVKNSQNPYED
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IIQAFSEIWHLLFM

>DCAR_017254 (DCARv2_Chr5:13671894..13672685)
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>DCAR_013429 (DCARv2_Chr4:30253465..30253995)
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>DCAR_020721 (DCARv2_Chr6:28906664..28907131)
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VEKDSDDPYLDFRRSMLQMLEKEIYSKDDLKELLGCFLLNSPYHHEIIVRAFTDIWNGLYSSY
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>DCAR_012074 (DCARv2_Chr3:43525622..43526404)
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SAAAYNNVVALEKMREEEYFNDDDDVELMKISSPLNG
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>DCAR_010451 (DCARv2_Chr3:23239734..23240519)
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KHCKPRHKHRRRRSQRKTRQKNNDKFDQFFTSVAANYGCVSSDDEKEEENASKYDDDTT
FFSSKSMSSDSSLAMEKSSTKQQWDNFDDDDDELTAKI
HADSAVIKRSSDPYDFRTSMVEMIVEKQIFGSKDLENLLHCFLSLNSLIHHRVIEVFTEIWETL
FSDWD

>DCAR_016895 (DCARv2_Chr5:8913728..8914282)
MTNIFRCSRPKSLISDVTEHPFFYPHSHFLFSPKKPPPSQPFSSICRPKTTQTAPVKPRHRKSR
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TNCWFSEDENEGKDDDRITLTFSGFKDSYAVVKRSSDPYNEFRTSMVEMIVERKLFKARELEHL
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>DCAR_025926 (DCARv2_Chr7:31757169..31758107)
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SPEETETLVSSSRSFSTDELETIREKPPKRHRYSR
KPKNKNLEPMTSSSRCSVTVSESESPARLSVFRKLIPCAVEGKVKESFAVVKKSVDPYEDFKKS
MSDMIFEKEMFEEKELEQLLQCFLSLNSRQHHGVIV
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>DCAR_018654 (DCARv2_Chr5:31914846..31915919)
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FELKPIITKINKVKKNDEEVSKIRMISATNDESISHSFYKEQKSVNSVKLSFNTNSTGVKLTDS
PRTASKRFLQGHHRKSASLGGARRSLAESFAVVK
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RDS

>DCAR_015345 (DCARv2_Chr4:13256186..13257259)
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FK

>DCAR_007928 (DCARv2_Chr2:38299219..38300714)
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EELLFTEWQNMKDAKINELMLKSEEQKRNVLRRDSS
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>DCAR_006331 (DCARv2_Chr2:24347085..24347852)
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EMEDELEEIIRGVRSDRLFFEPNSLLGSSTTTTTTTTGTAAATSDTRGASDDVCYNDVEELPFK
ESIVLAMESEDPYEDFKGSMLEMVESHGLKDWECE

ELLEWYLMNGKMNHGVIVQAFVDLLVGLASDDSTSFSSAASSFSASSSSPLSTVSRRELCNH
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>DCAR_012488 (DCARv2_Chr3:47514527..47515120)
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NPAGPGRD

>DCAR_018427 (DCARv2_Chr5:29731440..29732081)
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RRSMQEMVEARDLADAREQMDYLHDLTCYLSLNPKS
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>DCAR_002726 (DCARv2_Chr1:32323256..32323738)
MINPQTSPPHEDDRSHFLMKNFNSLYDPTTSHEPSSSPDFATAYASQRFFFSSPGRSNSIVD
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PTLSPDPYLDFFRRSMQDMVEARGFTDVKTNDNLHELLRCYLSLNPKSTHKYIVRAFADLLISL
MTTSPQP

>DCAR_030639 (DCARv2_Chr9:28494805..28495419)
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ELLLCYLTLNPKHHTHKFIKAFSDLLVSIMSSSESCP
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>DCAR_013428 (DCARv2_Chr4:30267772..30268701)
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>DCAR_002384 (DCARv2_Chr1:28822039..28822674)
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>DCAR_020722 (DCARv2_Chr6:28889122..28889910)
MSKKMKLPSPFKYTKSPSFPSTWPWPTCADPKAFSFRAENTTINSVVFVEEHSEFIASSSDSN
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FKESMKEMVEAHGLDGLDGLLEMLSCYLRVNGKCNH

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>DCAR_010565 (DCARv2_Chr3:25523639..25523953)
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>DCAR_016924 (DCARv2_Chr5:9159966..9160859)
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ANKISETS

>DCAR_016221 (DCARv2_Chr5:1326740..1327597)
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Carrot IQ-domain (IQDs) amino acid sequences with homology to tomato IQDs.

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Tomato IQDs amino acids sequences (allele name)

>SISUN1 (Solyc10g079240)

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>SISUN2(Solyc01g009340)

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>SISUN3 (Solyc01g088250)

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>SISUN4 (Solyc01g097490)

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VSTI

>SISUN5 (Solyc02g077260)

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>SISUN7 (Solyc02g087760)

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>SISUN8 (Solyc03g026110)

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>SISUN10 (Solyc03g083100)

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>SISUN12 (Solyc04g016480)

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>SISUN13 (Solyc04g050050)

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AITHRDFHLDNRPSPTAHKQNRPPSRQSPSTPRSKTGRIRPASPRVSNVDDDSRSMASQA SE
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>SISUN14 (Solyc04g081210)

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SDLVDAKQSESVIIAGFNDAKADVIPDEHALVIQTAVRAFLARRAQLKQKHITKLQAAVRGHLVR
RQAVGTLRCVQAIVKMQILVRARHTNRIAEESSIKEKLKKGKENSGBKSEFTYISISKLLSNSFAQQ
LLESTPRTKSINIKCDPSKSDSAWKWLERWMSVASPGNQSPQSELSADQQENEPIEHPSNLI
ENEVQLDSESMDFRQGEASLSAVPSESDNLITYDADSLDFQANIPFSPQPQNVDEKTSRD
DTFCSIPTQHKEAKALPETVPNSFPANTEVEREDTHSLELSETESKKILHGSRKASNPAFIAAQT
KFEELTLAAKSTKDSSLPNHKTEDESSEDTFSTITNHSFGARDAAPSENSVPHSTRAQVGGSE
CGTELSISSTLSDPDRSEVGGHVFEQELPSNGGTDHHSKNGYPHIEDDSTNDLSHSDYVQAGR
EDPTDDAKHVDVMVSSDLSPVEQKPENNSVNVQIEQEARTDRLDKSSPDASPRSHITVPESQG
TPSSQVSVNPKIRSEKSGSIPKRRSAPAGKKSPSKLNHAPGTTSSSEQLSKDHKNEKRRNSFG
STKAGLADQEARDNSTSSSLPSYMQATESARAKAIPNSSPRSSPDVHNKDEYIKKRHSLPGSN
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>SISUN15 (Solyc05g007130)

MGKSPGKWLRSLLPGKKSSKSGTSKKSSNEKASVISTNAALSGSSVHLPLISEPVACNAGGIKE
DSNFEKGGVTNEVILPSIERDGDEQNTCLTLPEDTEKMRLEQAATKAQAIVRGYLARRAFLRLK
GTIRLQAAVRGHLVRRQAVATLYCIHGIVKLQANIRGQIARRSSIGCELITKQGLEKQDAKQLDY
QRANASKLARELSTNGFTTKLLASLPTGMPLHLHYGQEEPNSSQEWLVRWTISQIWQPRSKLE
TLPGKKHQNAEADIAMSKHSVRKVHSHKMQNGSNHSTSSGSEKKKSSHLVNSVLQNPGEIK
KVKHSLKKTSSPILEKPVQSEVDTERKRQSHDKSSMASDEPLKNSEGTVENSTNVAPPPVVV
DDTITHLDILSVSDTHHKSTTDAADQKSITDNREDDTPVANEDFCTNHDNNEGSESNKVNRRVS
LPAKHVDVASTPTTRKVPSYMAPTKSAKAKLKEQASPRFGQDVAEKNAVTRRHSLPSPMNGK
LSSSPSPRVQRLVQASAKEGIKIDRSLSSSRDGTDKMTRAEWKR

>SISUN16 (Solyc06g052010)

MGKKGSGNWFSTVKKVFIKPSCKDYLPDTHKKEKLENQWQHEAREVVSVEKIPAESCSDLTIN
RESNENSSISSAEDRNHDHIVIEATVAAAEAATYTAPKTIKLDGHNHKSKEEIAATLIQSYRGYL
ARRALRALRGLVKLQALVRGHSVRKQAQMRCMQALVRVQSKVRARLQLRQSKVVEEVK
SRSSIREESLLLKQETHSIENTRRKQQVYNAYQKWLHSDLDDEECFGNEHENPQQSWNWLD
KWMASQHVVRQEDSSYVLSITDDISEKTFELGPEDVNLAHQNEKSPYSSTQSNKDSVPSYMA
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RVHDRTSLVGPPAHRYNYN

>SISUN17 (Solyc06g053450)

MGEKGSWFYALKRVFTCNKSKKSAYGSGKKTAKKGGRRILRHGEFKSFLFREPSSIEKILGE
VDDQNLLVRPPTSEQSGIPSAFPVAPTSPRINSPRDASPQSSYRATSPGVTSPRVASPRVVSP
KAASPKVTSPKEASPKVTSPREAYPKATSASAPSLKALSPREASPKANSASAPSQKATAPKEAS
PRVSSPRSTYPEPSRNHNEISYANRPEATLTLHLSATKIQAAYRSYMARRGFKSLSGLARLQGV
VRSRSVKRQTVNAMKQMQLLGRVQMCIQSRRSQMFQALHSQAYMNDKEVESTLSKWTQLTE
AGNHDDWNNSMLTKDEVEARRREKVEAVIKRERAMSAYSHQLWRRNPKSATDIRTSGIPW
WWNWLHHQLLPGNDSQSASVKDVHSTPSRAISEHKPSPWRLSQNFRHLHLDYDSHESVTP
RSTKSAPVPLRGKLMHTPRRTSSPMSSSSVSKYSRRRASAADSPFNHSMKDDDSLTCPPFSG
PSYMSPTISAKAKFRGKTILEERNIGTPSNSSRRRLSFPLTPSSTGSVKWNKGGSKDAASLKEH
ESMGDHMSVHSTGSTPTIVGRKPFQRFV

>SISUN18 (Solyc06g066430)

MKKDKENVDNMSNSSDKRDKKRWSFGKSSKESIGVGDNPVNFPGGVPVAVDSNWLRYSISEN
EKEQSKHAI AVAAATAAAADA AVAAAQA AVAVVRLTSQGRGAMFTGGREKWAAAKIQTVFRG
YLARKALRALKGLVKLQALVRGYLVRKRAAATLHSMQALIRAQA AVRSQRARRSMTNDTRNQF
ETRARRSIERFDEYRSEFHSKRLSTSNDSYDGFDESPKIVEIDTFRTKSRSRMNNACMSES
GDEQHSQAMSSPLPCPLPARLSIPDCRHLQDVNWSFLADEQCKFASAQTTPRFAGSGRSNAP
PTPAKSICGDGYFRAYANFPNYMSNTQSFRAKLRSHSAPKQRPEPGPKRRLSLNEIMASRTSF
SGVRMQKSCSQVQEEYCF

>SISUN19 (Solyc08g007920)

MGKASKWFKALLGFKKNESISSSTNKKKWGDVKS YKDKDFQQHHEKSHYMNSRAGVDLAIYE
VHSSLTSSVIRTTTWNSEEWAAVVIQSYFRAYLSRRALRALKGLVKLQALVRGHIVRKQAADM
LRRMQALIRAQSRARLGRSMVFESPPFSTKSTQSIHHGPTTSSRCTRSTGPFPTPKSSTRSY
TSDEYSNNHPNYMSYTEAAKAKTRSMSAPRLRSQYDKKYARSNMQ

>SISUN20 (Solyc08g007930)

MGKASKWFKALLGFKKNDSSISSSTNKKKRGDVKS YKDKDFQQHHEKSHYMNSSAGVDPAYIE
VHSSLTSSVIRATMWSGEEWAAVVIQSHFRAHLRRALRALKGLVKFQALARGHIVRKQAAD
MLRRMQALIRAQSRARLGRSMVFESPPFNAKSTQSIHHGPTTSSRCTRSTGPFPTPKSSTRS
YTSDEYSNNHPNYMSYTEAAKAKTRSMSAPRLRSQYDKK

>SISUN21 (Solyc08g014280)

MGKKGSWFSAIKRVFTPSSKEKLPNESEKKGAKKKNRGKLGKHGETKSFIFLREPSSIEKILGE
VDEEMLLSPRFTLPAGAVSPRISSYRFATPTATSPRVASPKASSRRVTSPKAPSQRVTSPRAIS
PKAHPRPVSPNVSRNRKEISYAYRPEPTLRALNLSATKIQAAYRGMARRSFRALRGLVRLQ
GVVRSNVKQKTANAMKQMQLLVRVQTQIQSRRIQMLENQALQHQAYKNDKDVESTISKWTQ
LCEAGNNDNWDDSLTKEEVEGRLRKKVEAVIKRERAMAYAYSHRLWKNDPKSGLDMGANG
FPWWWNLWLERQLPSRNANKTPSAMKDIKLTTPRAISEHKPSPTPLNNVTFRRILSDYDNNESS
VTPMSTKSAIPMRGKQMHTPIRTPPMNSSLKKYSRGRASASNYPFDLPLKDDDSLTS CPPFS
VPHYMSQTASATAKAKARANSNPKERNPEKQSNDTKKRFSFPLTPNIWSSKWSKSGSGKDSAS
RKEVDKHESMADHISVDSTVSM PAVVGGRRPFNRFV

>SISUN22 (Solyc08g062940)

MGASGKWVKALIGFKKSEKEDHEKKVKKWKIWRSDVKGLKQRNGVVGSEGSDCSSMNDAYT
AAVA AVVRAPPKDFKAVREEWAAIRIQTFRGFLARRAFRALKGLVRLQALVRGRQVRKQAAV
TLRCMQALVRVQARVRARRVRMSIEGQAVQKILEEHRGKLDPMKEAEEGWCD SKGTLEEVKT
KIHMREQEVLKRERALAYSQAQKQSKSSQNFDSRTTISVPSLKNLDYDKSNCGWSWLERWMA
ARPWENRLMEQAYTDSMETTPKSKACLETLDKEKATTEPCSVKVKKNVTKRISAKPLI

>SISUN23 (Solyc08g080470)

MGKASKWFRGLLGLKKQDPSSSSNQNPKPTKKKWSFVKSYREKDSNFVKGTDKESSNYGRV
VSNLQNGAVGCSVDSSKRAIAVAEATAVVAEAAIAAAQAAA AVVKL TNSGRATTATNGGAAA
VTTWNGVSLTSSAVGCKRKGVAAAGNRENWAAVVIQSHFRAYLSRRALRALKGLVKLQALVRG
HIIRRTADYLRQMQAISRAQSRARAGRSQVSGSPHSSTKSVQFVHDPTTPEKFEHVIRARSLK
HDETSVLKRNTSKSNWKVIDSEKARIRPQGSSARTSSIDDEKSDKILEIDTGKPYVTPKQRNLFH
SSHLCLNSDQYSYSLTTSKESTAHQTVSPSSCGNQPLSPLKFNE DLDEACFCTADNSPQFYS
ASSKGGSSKRGPFTPTKSDGSRSYMSGYSDHPNYMSYTESSKAKVRSMSAPKQRPHYERSS
STKRYSIHGYSESRNNSQKGSFYANFTGKAYPGSGLDRLGMPVIRADPSGFSGGLRHRY

>SISUN24 (Solyc08g083240)

MGKKGATSWLSAVKRAFRTKDNCDKAKIEHQLDEDEEKRDKRRWLF RKQSQSEGK
AMVDPKHAI APEAAVATDQAAL EIRL TRSNKYSPSNAAVLIQTA FRGYLARRALIALK GIVKLG

ALIRGQNVKQAKMTLKCMQALLRVQARVREQRARLSHDGGRRSMFAETTNLWDSKYLRDIR
DRNSRSRDGSSIADDCPRSLVELESMLQARKEASFKREKSLAHAFTQQELDEMDIVCSEERNE
RELEETANWLDEWMSSKQWNRGSFDRRDSIKTVEMDTAKPYCNMVPNARRSQHSSPLHRQA
SSPHYTANSPHHQRSSHYNSAIQPPATPPPCQPKPLQMRSTSPRKSQSTANTPCLRSTSR
NSIMSRYSTSGNDASVPNYMAATESAKARIRSQSTPKQRPSTPERERVGAVKKRLSYPIPEPYT
GYGYSQNLRSFSKSLQAAYVGMEQQSCYTDSLGGEISPCSTTDLRRWLR

>SISUN25 (Solyc09g007410)

MEKKGSWFSSVKKALSPDPKEKVDKKASKSKKKWFGKEKHTLVDSSTAVTATASPPHPVPL
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QTAFRGYLARRALRALRGLVRLKSLVDGPTAKRQTTNALKCMQTLSRMQSQISSRRIRMLEEN
RTLQRQLMQKHVKELESLRRGEEWDDSLQSKERVEASLLSKYEAAIRRERALAYSYSHQQTW
KKSSRSTNLLFMDPTNPQWGWSWLERWTGARPWESQSMSEKQLKTDQMSVRSVSIAGGEIA
KSFARHQLNSELPSSPSRQKPSHPSRYHSPPTTSPKPTTSVAAARKLKPASPRISAMNQDDDN
SMLSVQSERNRHSIAGSSIRDDESLASSPSVPSYMASTQSAKAKTRLQNPGLMENGKPEKG
SAGSVKKRLSYPPSPARTRRHSGPPKFDNTSLNTSIAEDHVNGVVN

>SISUN26 (Solyc09g082560)

MGKTGRWIKNLLIGKKDKDKDKLEGEKIQNSITSNEHQPTTPIPIPSTTPKDKKRWSFRRSSA
TPPGQRDLSTGDIVATTTAKQELLESNDNHKKHVLAVAAATAAADAAAAAKAAAAAIQFTAA
ARAYALEEDAASKIQAVFRGYLARKALNALKGLVKLQALVRGHLVRKQAAATLRCMQALVTVQ
ARARAQRIRMTEEENPNPRQSVHRKSTQDNKFRHSYQDYEEEDIKIVEMDLGESKGNTKSRN
CYSNQGQTERTEHRFSTHNAYTNQEHQHIIISPVPSAITEQSPKAYSGHFEDYTSYPTTHSSP
QYYNNTMSKPDPSRILYSSYARSEYAEPESELYNEYPFYSYMANTKSSIAKARSHSAPKQRPD
QTSFERQPSRRRPSIEGRNVPRAVRMQRSSSHVGSTAQNYQYPWSIKLDKSNISINDSECGSN
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>SISUN27 (Solyc10g005000)

MGNNKKGSSSSWLSAVKRAFRSKKQINEEEKKKENQRKQHTTNHNAQAATIIQTAFRGYL
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TSHQHMSSTIPDDWDERPHTIEEVKAMLQKRKEAAFMKCQGTQPFSSQTRRSRSGSSIGSDAD
FGEKRAAAKSWDSSSRGRASTYPVEMDTSQRNLITRLHQRPTSPLHTSFQFPVTPSPSKSTRP
IQVRSASPRHDKKSQTPSLRPNNYSSYQPNRLTSSAAIPNYMAATESALARIRSQSAPRQR
PSTPERDRAGSAAKRLSFPVPDRYGNVPSAYGHNLRSPSFKSLSGVHFGEYQSSNYSSCYTE
SIGGEISPSSTDFRRYLR

>SISUN28 (Solyc10g008790)

MSGGYWLKKVISLRKAKDGRSKRLKGTSGRKEDEHSQKEPSRRTNGASVKKHREMGIPISED
NAAIRIQTAFRAYMARKTLRRLKRISRLRSMIQGPSVKKQASTTLSALHSWNRIQAEIRACRVRM
VIEGRLKQKLENQLKLEAKLHNLEVEWNGGPETMEVVLSRIHQREAAAVKRERTMAYAFSHQ
WRANSNPMFGSSIHDLGKANWGWWSKDRWIAARPWESRIPVQSSPKIANRTASKTPKSYKTQ
TTKTPVSVKSTSANRKRAMPKPRKLSYEAADKL TALKGINKVETSIDKQEVAS

>SISUN29 (Solyc10g084280)

MGKKGSWFSSVKKALSPNSKEKKGKSKKKWFGKEKQPLPDSSTLVASVSPQPPIQVEEV
KLAEEVEEQTKHVYSVAVATAAAAEAAVAAAQAAAEVRLTTVNQFPGKSKEEIAAIRIQTFRG
YLARRALRALRGLVRLKTLVDGPTVKRQTANTLKCMQTLSRAQSQISSRRSRLLEENRTLQRQ
LMQKHAKLELESLRRGEEWDDTLQSKEQIEASLLGRYEAMRRERALAYSYSHQQTWKKSSKA
TNLLFMDPTNPQWGWSWLERWWMGARSRENQNMSEKELKGDQMSVRSASMSMSGGEITKAF
ARHQLNSELPSSPLSQKPNRPSSRQSPTTSPKPTARKPKPGSARVSAINQEDDTRSVFVSVQS

EMNRRHSIAGSSVRDDESLGSCSSVPSYMASTQSAKARTTRLQSPLGVENGTPPAKGSAGSV
KKRLSYSPSPAITRRHSGPPKVEITSTNTSNAEKYVNGVVN

>SISUN30 (Solyc10g086060)

MGKKGWFWSSVKKALSPDPKSKKKWYGKEKDPVPDSFSPVAASVSPHPVPHVEEVALDEV
EEELTKHAYSVAASTSAAAEVDVSATEAAEEVVWLDKVTQYTGKSKEEVAAIKIQTAFRGYLAR
RALKALRGLVRLKSLADGPTGKRQTAHTLKCMQTLSRVQSQISSRRIRMLEENRALQRQLMQK
HAKELESLRRGEEWDDSAQSKEQIEASVLSKYEAARRRERALAYSYSHQKTWKKSPRSANLLF
MDPTNPQWGWSWLDRWMGAKPWDTQSMSEKEHKNDQMSVRSASIAGGEITKAFARYQLNS
DLPSPSSQKPSHQSPPTPSKPANSTASRKLKSARVAAISQDDDARSMISMQSERNNRRHSIGV
ASIRDDESLGSSSSVPSYMIPTKSAKAKTRLQNPGLMENNSTPEKGPAGSVKKRLSYPPSPAR
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>SISUN31 (Solyc11g071840)

MGVSGKWIRALVGLKKSEKSHSSEKEENKSGGTGKFWHRRKHSVEIDSNLLQKELTYNDAGA
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QALVRGHAVRKQAAITLRCMQALVRVQARVRARRVRMSLESQTEQQKVEQQLEHDARVREIE
EGWCDSVGSVEIQEQKLLKRQEAAAKRERAMAYALAHQWQAGSRQQATLSGFEPDKSSWG
WNWLERWMAVRPWENRFLDLNVRDGVMPNENESAEPVNGMKNQVKVAGKKPATTTLNDR
VGPSHSSSNSKSNEKAAASLSDGCSPPNVSASTQETPAALVNPKSKPNREDLVEEASSKPV
LGRSHSNPKERSTPSDKQKQRLSLPGSGLAPQTARQPSRTIKRTSSTQKPLKEKSKLNETD
TKSTATVSQQAAD

>SISUN32 (Solyc12g008520)

MGKAIKWLKGLFGIKKLEIDEKGKIGTTFCFHSGRDTTAVAAVSDRLCHNPPTIPPNTIPAEAAW
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IQTVFRGFLARKALRALKGLVKLQALVRGYLVRRQANATFHSMQALMRVQASVRALKINGGFY
VNHQNSQFQQRKSIEKFEESRSGSTKQMSSRRLSSSFEANNINEESAKIVEMDTGRPКСRSRR
TNTWASNPCDDPFEQVLSSWASDWAQQPVGTAQSTPRFANSCGSNTPTAKSVCVESKYFRN
NNYYDTNNNYPNYMAKTQSFKAKLRSHSAPKQRPGLSRVKKMSLNEMMESRVSSSGVKM
QRSCSQAQEKISINFKNVMSKLG NSTEGERDF

>SISUN33 (Solyc12g014130)

MIGLKRNRKRKSKQLKITSTSTAFDEPKGDVQVPSAHYSNGTSSSKKITCKTKFTHNTAATKIQT
AYRAHLARKTLRRVRGAVRFQGVIEGLSVNNQISGTLKQIHCWSKIQSEIRARRLNMVTQGHNK
QKKIQNQKLEAKLHELEVEWSSSAETIEEILQKLQQREEAATKRERAMAYAFSHQWRANSNK
YFGQAYYDLGKESWGWSWMERWIAVRPWETRVQTNPIVPKTSHSQQVAKITSKATNLGPMKL
VVSINKH

Tomato OFPs amino acids sequences (allele name)

>SIOFP1(Solyc02g085510)

MGKSLKLRFSRVIASFNSCRKNPSSLPQNPFFPHKLTSTKHISPDFPLIDQNQNQNHRNYVP
ESTMISVGCCRSEFKWEKEEFHVVSSSFVSEEEEECEEEINLALRPPLTPPRFSRIVVEKKKKK
QQRVKKTKTKSRIIRMSTSSADEYSGILSGTNTDWDNNEEETESLVSSSRSCYDFSSDDSSSTDF
NPHLETICETTTMRRRHKRNANTKRRSIKQSRPSFSSSKGRRSSVSTSSDSELPARLSVFKKLI
PCSVDGKVKESFAIVKKSQDPY

>SIOFP2 (Solyc01g007800)

MSTHRRRIILSNVTVKLGCSSSCIRPKLSSIFHPKPRKSPKSQTQNKNYSNYSSCSSWDTTTTTT
SPNSDSTTNESSDFKTSKAVQGGFRIGGESVAVEKDSDDPYLDFRQSMQMLEKEIYSKDDLK
ELLNCFQLQNSPYYHGIIVRAFTEIWNGVFSLRPGVAGASSPFLHGGSHVTYR

>SIOFP3 (Solyc01g007810)

MKLSLFLKNSSQNSSSTTTTTTPWPWSLPTCGKPKTLSFRLEKNQHNIYNSTFHLDDINDTTSCS
FDDFFSEIDETSSSSTTTINGQDCIEKVIKGLRLEKERLFFPEETSSILDFQENKNISITSSNININ
VVDEGNIISFVPMGLDSNDPFVDFRKSMEEMVEAYEIKDWENLEELLTCYLKVNCKSNHGYIVG
AFVDLLVNLATFSDNNNNVGVGDIGAGVGAGVDESTIIMTTIDEEQQCLSSTTTTTTTTTNHSFTS
PLSFCSSSCSTSSSITSTSACLSSLLEEDEVITKHH

>SIOFP5 (Solyc02g072030)

MKWGKKKPPSSSLMTHVFPVSWLSKFKQKKVCRSEDQEGAKMRKVDLRTNVCLKQGRFYEDD
PYWRISFSEENHPQNPLWCGECDQNSKSSLGEENHKFNDMVSRKISEKPKNEAEFSNRKRNS
VKDEKLRKLSRKALEERIAENAREEVTEKDIFEIPEDEKVMKRGKEKPTAYKSRKARLSYND
SSPNSVEESCMMFTSLNLEEEADALSEEEFESECLKIKEMSEKSGCQQRKSVYINQRRRKHG
IKVRAYSPTAKMECRIKALEDMMKARMKTRHETKESFTGDRTVFDSYAIMKSSFDPFSDFRDS
MIEMITQRGIKSSEEELELLACYLTLNCDEYHDIKIVFRQVWFELNQINIGEELQKCCCSDE

>SIOFP6 (Solyc03g034100)

MAKLLKFRISKAINSFHSCRSKDPCTLPQHPVPSFLQNTQFITDDHLLFEEMIQQNNESQLIST
HHEHFPIITSPSFKHHVSVTPITATGQCSSRNGEAFSTTSSDSTRSPSHEFKWKKEEDKWQH
FIKTNSDDDTKQQPRRKISYSFSSDSDNDKILIEIKKISTSKTNFFMMMSTTSSSSSMDENEIN
FTSKKTKWDYHEDIDITNEDEENETETFISSSRKSHVEFPDSSLNFSHEFDTIYKNTTRRCQKK
IGYSKRRDHVKNTRSRSSRDMMNIGRRSSISTSTTSSDGELPPRLSVFKKLIPCNVEGKVKESF
AIVKKSDEDPYEDFKSSMMEMILEKKIFEKNDLEQLLQCFLSLNAKNCHGVIVEAFSEIWETLFS
NHN

>SIOFP7 (Solyc03g120190)

MPKQLQKSLSDYLTKKKKATAQQTNSANKTLSSSTSWLLRGCRHPKTPSFSVAVDRKEKNV
QGENEAATLADVDRFVFNFKSFYKDDDNEAEIVENPNLSLSESPRHIIPLNHTGSRRFFIAPG
SSSSLIEEARTSMTVSDDTGSTSAITTTVTNTNSNELSAISTEYSKETLNANDFITLVYSPSPYD
DFRQSMQEMMEARLKDQGKINWEFMEELLFCYLDLNDKKSYYILSAFVDQVILRENSGRVPA
ISRNVRLDGLNQRDT

>SIOFP8 (Solyc03g120790)

MEESYKKIEPQMLLKKTIQKTKNFLYRTPHNLKSFLFGGHHKLPKTACHFNPFLSVSKRFSSSK
RIPKTNVKELDLRYDYQQWNQPDHNEIQERKMTSKNARKFQGMAEGDYSESQRELAVRFG
MEDIESERRKEDEKKGREVLTRSTSKGSLTLLKKMEELEMVEGEDMDHVLDIEEVLQCYTLLNS
PVYVDIVDRFFMDMYTEFSIRKPSGSVNSSMRRLGPLKL

>SIOFP9 (Solyc04g080210)

MTRRFKLLKLSMPSFRFCRPPKASFLPKSPMPLSLYKFS PANILDNSPVPVPPSTPHHPYILRKA
HNLASKTYNSPSESSEYSDPDNNMRRGESRKSRLNMSFSSVDSGWFSFNSECCDEKPNDETE
SFMSSPSFESSFDVDHGDPLSGIRRKNNNNTKVRRLRRLYLSNSLKDSMMPCMADGKVNES
FAIVKRSVDPYDDFKNSMKEMIMEKEMFEAEDLEQLLLCFLSLNSRHHHAIIVEAFTEIWEELFG
KSSKSMCLKLPRFQ

>SIOFP10 (Solyc05g055220)

MAKKLKISSFKKKELGLATWQWPSCTHSKTLSFRGDDNIFKTINSVFFDPFDGIETPQSYSTNS
SLDTNSISIESHEEIIKGARSERLFFEQVATSSIFQEPQEENQENDLPFKESVILAMESKDPYLDL
KKSMKEMVESQGIKDWDNLQELLACYLKLNGEVNHGFVLGAFVDLLVELVIPTTSTNSDNSIT
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>SIOFP11 (Solyc06g073040)

MVNYKGGKLLKHQRNRVSFSAKLPEDVRGAFADSTCVVKYSMDPLTDIKESIKEMVKNVGIKD
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>SIOFP12 (Solyc06g074020)

MTRKYDQCLVDNMFPGPFPECCPDEALEMAKQALATRRLSFEENESCSVLSMVGFPPFKDCLL
LAVETENPKMDFLHSMEQMTKVYGAQRGDMVDWEFMEELLTWFLKINNMKNQHFIVAFAFIDL
LGGHVQDVEPVENVEPLTDDIVNVILEELWWGL

>SIOFP13 (Solyc06g082450)

MNTSCCLKFNPCPKIVKLFKFKLRKPLFIRRLRIFRPSTRCESNTSTRRKQASQVLSVFRFIRR
SKPREEDQVMALKSFSGHIKAPVSPITPAYARLSGATKKEVVIFQDDVEDACRSFENYLAEMIV
EEGKMRDIMDVEELLYCWKNLKS PVIDLVCRFYGELCKDLFSHTYKDDINSPQKIMQ

>SIOFP14 (Solyc06g082460)

MGNHKKFSDMMPNTWFYKLDMSKTKNHSKPFSSSSTNKSQYSQPRSSFSYTRRSIRVDKI
YNHSYNFLDQPRSSSSSSSKKSKRKTIIKPSPKHIPSSVTNYVSVSNKLNSSSVYSTEEDK
FPELDFLNSPSEFDSVDSQTFNELPSTWPNSCNCHFTSSATDIIIDVNDKALSNEFHNLTTTEYA
EFSIDIDLPIFTKASNSIKNIKQDENVKAQREKEPKNRVGSPPSRKHYSSSSGVKLRTNSTKV
ANKRNSVSSSKRRSKTKKESCSASRGTSFAIVKASIDPEKDFRESMVMVENNIRASKELLENL
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>SIOFP15 (Solyc07g055240)

MQNSKAAVAAAANKKQKLGCSALCCSRLSVSSSSEEAESSSSSRYP TISSLTHAMVQERLDK
MIREREEAKNEEMRRRRRRAERDEKTKFIVMIAMEKSSYDPREDFRESIEQMIIANRICDPKDLR
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>SIOFP16 (Solyc08g068170)

MDNHIVNKFSRLFPSSFTSCQFRNIPDVVENSFIISKNSKFVHNNAVGVSSRTNSSIKTQESKSN
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CYELSVNSVSRVGSNLGESKWWKSRNGTSKTEQNGGKVSRTLRETGGTSRKKYGSEMSHC
SATLSRTNGRVGSNLDESKWVKSINGLDFASAKTEQNRGKTSRTARKTANQNDSEMSPPSSA
LWRTNERVHSNLDESKWVKSINELDFTTSKTEQNRGKAESKWWKSINELDFASSNTEQNRGKP
IRTARKTANQNDSEMSHSSSEL SMINEQVNSNLDELKRVKSINELDFTISKTEQNRVNTSRKTP
PRSSRRTLKTTTPVEKFDYYSDFTSNTRRKTTCRRKIKKSSSTSSDEMGRKIVIEGRIEESIAV
EKNTNDPHNDFRTSMLEMIVEKQIFGLKDLQRLHCFSLNSPSFHKIIFEVFAEIFETLFH

>SIOFP17 (Solyc09g018200)

MGNYRFKLSDMVTSSWFYKLDMAKSRTQIKRKQTSSTSSSSFSIFYSSSNVQQHHRKSYFF
SRTLSPNPHQSNVTPMKSSKRNTRRNTPKFVNPKSMILSPSHRRCNDHIFDSVSKIDLPPIL
TKPNKKEEKTELKFLTVKTEQSTSPKRISVSSSSTGVKLRKTKSPRIISRRSVGEKSYAVVKSSK
NPQKDFKESMVEMIVKNNIKTSKDLEELLACYLLLNSHHYHHLIITVFKQIWFDLQLK

>SIOFP18 (Solyc09g065350)

MPRTTLGTNFNLCFTKLRSLPLRSIDDNDNDNDNERHQQQHSMHFCNSVKNFNSLYDLSS
SECNIPTSSSTDESDYNYELENTPDLATYASQRFFFSSPGHSNSIIDSSSSSISSSIASSTSSSVG
SDAPLEGASRFQRIHPTRIWIWIFDDRCKKWWRHVD

>SIOFP19 (Solyc09g082080)

MPRILQKKFYHCLPSFKCLPTILSLPFEETEEEEKTEQKKIKNFNSVFDIPSSDSATTSKSLTNSST
TTTEEDNNTNCTFTSFEDSDYTNIPDFSNIFASQRFFFSSPGNSNSIIDFPPENPKVVTGGVAV
QTYSPDPYSDFRSMQEMVEAHEL TNVKANWGFLHELLLACYLNLNPKHHTHYIIRAYSIDLVLVSL
MSMDDSEKKTEGIARP

>SIOFP20 (Solyc10g076180)

MGNYRFRLSDMMPNAWFYKLDMAKSSSRHSHTTSSSNLQLDKKRQPHNNLGCQRKSYII
SRNLTITSPISSNSPKLDHNVHITEPSRKSYSKRRSTNFRRRNSPKPVNSSASVESVWTKPDST
PEQYPNSSSSSSSSPSSILPHKSNPIASISPCDCRDTYTNQNSANLDPGVHSVSKIDLPRITK
PEKFNEKIQEKQRIVKQEQRIVRRVSTNGVKLRNTNSPRITTTTTNSRKSVSCKRTSVTTDSFAVV
KSSRNPQKDFRESMVEMIIENNITTSKDLEELLACYLSLNSDEYHDIIVKQIWFTEIRLK

>SIOFP21 (Solyc10g082050)

MSTTKKRVILRNVTVKLGCSSSCIRPKFSSIFHPKPRRHHSADSAAVFNHHKTPNPKYSFSNSTI
TTATTFSPSPTPSPAHYSSDAERAVQGFGRIGGESVAVEKDSDDPYVDFRQSMLQMLEKEIYS
KDELRELLNCFQLNSPYYHGIIVRAFTIWHCVFSVNPVGTGAESPFL

>SIOFP22 (Solyc10g082060)

MNLSSLFKSKKKSSFSPFLCPLPHCGIPKTLSLRVENNDNIFNSQRLYNVDDDMVDMVEGLK
IEKDRFFFEAGEKTSSIMKVSSSILAKSNELEILPIDESCIVTIDSMIDPCGEGAISIRDQVSSST
LSNNTNNSGKQVEYLPFNDSCIIKLSMMDPYGSFKKSMVKMVEANLGIKWNEFLEEMLAWY
LEVNEKNHKEYIIGAFCDLWISYSFTSSTNIPNSFLFSSEPKSVISPTSTSFVIS

>SIOFP23 (Solyc10g083070)

MKFSSLFKSNKKPSFSPMLCRLPRCGDLRTLIRDENNHNIFNSQRFYNNVDDDEMDEVIESLK
LEKDRFFVEAGQKTSILDMSSSRLSKKRTISKRLEFLPFNNDSCVITSMDSIDAYGETSRSILEG
SSSRLSKSTNNSTSSKRLGYLPSNDSMDSYGDQETSSILDMSSSSSNDNISSKGLGYLPSNES
MDATSILERSKSNSSHGFVYYVPCKKTYAIMRLISRDPYEDIKYFLEKMVDENLEIEDWEEESLEE
LCGWLLEINEKNIHKYIVGAFCDLWMSYSCTSTINTPFGFSSSKPPSLYFMSLIENEADRMIAAS
TSSVTP

>SIOFP26 (Solyc10g083080)

MEFFSLFKSKKKPSFSPMLCRLPRCGNLRTLIRDENNHNIFNSQRF CINVDDDIVDEVIEGLKF
EKKRFFFESGEKTSSILNVSSSKLSK SIGNKRLEFPSPDESCVITHIDSIDAYGETSTRSIFKSSS
RLTKNDYSTSNNKFESLPLNNSCVISPSAMRVTSIDPYGYIKKYMEITVEENQGIKWKESELKEI
CAWYLENNDNDKNIHKFIIGAFCDLWMSYSSTNTNTPFGFSTSEPPSPYFMSLIEAKADQIIAT
STSSVIP

>SIOFP27 (Solyc10g083090)

MKFSSSLFKSKKKPPFSPMLCRLSRCGNLRTLIRDENNNHIFNSQRFYNNVDDDEMDEVIEENLK
LEKDRFFVESGQKTSSLLDMSSSRLSKRRTISKRLFLPFNNDYVITLMDSIDAYGETSRILE
GSSSRLSKSTNNSTSSKRLSYRPSNDSMDSYGDQETSSILDMSSLSNDSISSNGLGYLPSNE
SMDATSILERSKSNSSHGFVYYVPCCKTYVIMRLISRDPYEDIKYFLERMVDENLEIEDWKESLE
ELCGWLLINEKNIHKYIVGAFCDLWMSYSCTSTTNTPFENSSKPPSLYFMSMIEDEADQMIA
ASTFSVIS

>SIOFP28 (Solyc10g083100)

MKFFSLFKSKKKPSFSPMLCRLPRCGNLRTLIRDENNNHIFNSQRF CINVDDDIVDEVIEGLKF
EKKRIFYEAGEKTSSILDVSCAITHIDSIDAYGKTSTRSILKGTKSRLSKNDNSTSNDMVESLPLN
DSCVITPSVMRVTSIDPYGYIKKHEMMVEENQGIKDWKESLKEICALYLEINYIDKNIHRFIIGAF
CDLWMSYSGTSTTNTPF GFSTSEPPSPYFMSLMEA

>SIOFP29 (Solyc11g006670)

MGKKMNLGSWQWPSCHTSKTQSFRANHIFKTINSIFLDPSNTDHHHHGVVEIETTPESWFTNS
SESASFSTESEETGEPLMELIIGVRSERLFFEPNCTSSSILEHQDQSQDQNNQNNQSQSQSR
DQDQSQSQSQEKLKEIEEDVDEELPFKESVALALESEDYPYLDFFKKSMEEMVDTHEIKDWESLQ
ELLQWYLMNGKNNHGFIIIGAFVDLLIGFTPSNCDSITCYSSAASSFSIE
EKGE

>SIOFP30 (Solyc11g068780)

MSSKNKKIWNCITSNGTAGCGCSKPKLSEIIQPKPKPRPEPEPNAHSSSTSNSDSPSPTIMPAKI
VGSVAVVKDSDDPF GDFRRSMLQMIMEKEIYSYDDLNELLNCFLLQNSPSHHDIILQAFMEIWN
NGKNYIAN

Tomato TRMs amino acids sequences (allele name)

>SITRM5 (Solyc07g008670)

MDGMDDRRMGCMGGFLQLFDRNHILAGKRLYSTKRLPHFTVPDDVSESDKFVASPAVSKELV
KPQPQLDQSKQAAVGVISVEPVVSVSVETPPKSPLPLPIFEVKEGTRSSWKFCKEAPRLSLDSR
AVVDAKGSLRPRELRTKGSVLSASRGENTEEGVVADGDDNQRPCPSVIARLMGLEPLPQSNN
ETLPKSELRRSASESRVSRDLFNGRYVDGNNVDFKELNNTRANVSNNAMKDNAVNERSTMP
NARPTDRMGYPLKNENTERQKASNRSLSSSPWKSPQHRKFFFDADIFPEPKQTVSLYGEIDK
RLKMRGIDEPSKDLETQILEALQLKGLLHNKRPSEQIGHRFVYDPTLSSDESPVLMRPSRS
VSPSHRRMANGTSPSSLRNRNGIGRRLNLSSSELPSVSPCRERPATERNARSPLRSKDSSTPT
QRENSVRLSSSVAKPKNLNVDSRRRAGEPAENRRVSPVQSPKLSRRNSLEHNGAKRSPRNR
RETTESKQKEKITTFVTEDESSSISESTVSSSFQTAERSNLEDYNEGRSLLERCCKLLNSIAEM
TAPESQPSPVSVLDSSFYRDDSPSPSPIMKRNIDFKDVSGESEEIWLAFSPVRSKCNDSMD
DTHLGYISDILRASCYLPEDSDVFLLEKQQYLKGGKDTSKVSRLQRKLIFDTITEILDRNRQLPPW
KAFSLSGSSIAKPSLEGIWSEFQRIQERESGNLVEIICEVLKDLAQDVTNNGWGDPCVEMSEA
VLDMERQIFKDLIVETIQDLAVIGFKTLLTASRRKLVF

>SITRM19(Solyc09g005750)

MEKSRHRKSRASGVMEGSKLAQKQVATPEVTLNSRSYCDEATRGMIMHDFGKSSSKRVT
GTPIKNLLAEEMAREGESKKRPTSIVARLMGLEGMPSQHQHGRQRRFSDSCQHRNEHIDSRR
RKQLFDEQSSKRSSMEHQEFKDVYEDLEASHVGNRRHSSRWNETGRFATPDMALIQQKFM
AKRLSTDERFQNSKEFNDTLEALDSNKEKLLKYLQEPDSLQVHLQDLQVESASSKCSRIAVLK
PSNSVKYEGSAKSSKSVRGGGCKKKSISLQKE
RLDGLLLQSQRHSGHNSQKSSPVLSEGKEENILPTRIVVLKPNLGITQSNIASVPHHPDERKH
AKYL RASPGGAGEEEEEKNSSKNMGIYRPKSNEARDIAKEITRRMRDSFGPFDGRDAYFRGSG
VKGYAGDESSCDIY
ESDSTGDSDIATLSCRKSSGRGNLKKSSSLGSESSVGREAKKRLSERWKMTQYYQDIEMAGK
SNTLGEMLSLPDGVTKHDYCDTMVHVEEATKEPGGRKGTTEWDFPLGISSRDGWKDVCI
SGYRSTSPFFSKHR
TRARREFSNKQCSVSKEPVNQEQSVNHHSRSLDGMVNLRDEFSSKNSRSSKKKLHSRQLVS
DTSSKGLRQRIDMNLKEDLSEKLSLASQVPSADGMSYTNASDDAETDSITLSSEYSVEMHRK
LPAECGSASPINQEV
SILQEALPEPSPTSSAAASVVLEYPAPEPESSISSKGADHRSPVLEYPAPEPESSVSSKEADH
PSPPSVLEVPFTEDVSSGSECFERVS AELNGLRMQLKLLKMESGPYADVILSDDEVESFEDNC
SLRSQSWQSSYI
LDVLTDSGLKTSDPDTFVTSFHTLECPSPWVFDNLEKKYDDETTGPRYERLLFDRINLGLLEI
VRKYVDPCPWVKPIEGIIWRWETYGMKNILHQLLRSHEDPANADTPGNVVEEMHWLAIKDEMD
VAVKDIEELLID
DLIEEVGAV

>SITRM17/20a(Solyc06g083660)

MLIFSFRLLCREMTGGEMNGFQNGKNCNLDKPPFGCLGRMVNLFDLNSGVTGNKLLTDKPH
GSLRSQS
DVVRMYPGSGNQIEEKMIVSDLKRNSSNRKSNGTPMKMLIAQEMSKEIDSSQNPPSLVAKLMGL
DAFPTRK
SVSATQSHFGGHSRSHDSSFSYCPHENGLMEEMHQEFHQCEENEYKDVYEVWQQPTKI
NCVRSKSPQ
KARHDETSIDKKVAFVRQKFIEAKCLSIDGNLRQSKEFQEALDVLSSNTDLFLKFLQEPNPMFSQ
QLQKL

KSVPPPPETKRITVLRPTKMVDNSRFGESGNKNEKEMKRATQVGQGNRVDESHCPVSPAPG
WNDENPAQ
PTRIVVLKPSLTKTRNCMAASSPPSASPRVSEAEMKYVNIEDNEAQDSGEVALSQKMHENLGG
HRRDETL
FSSMSSNGYIGDESSFNKSENEYVAGNLSDEVISPVSRHSWDYINRFVEPYSCSSLSRASYS
PESSVSR
EAKKRLSERWAMVSSNGSFPEQRHLRRRSSTLGEMLALSDTKHAGGMEQEISKEEPGTSYSN
LMNNSNCD
EGIDESPRNLLRSKSVPVSSSEFGTLLNADVPGHETGKPNLPEETTKPRSTKLSLKNLLFSRNR
KPSKDN
GRHLQSNNEVQSGVKSSYCPAKVDLGREFSSADLHKSPGKLVSONSFGEQGIISPEVGLFVSK
SLPLENQ
CESQDEPSPISALDITFEDEHSACISFGRTKPDHGGELSVDPIRCNLIDKSPPIGSIARTLSWN
DSCID
TASSVPLRPFLSTWRTEEEEEKWFVQTLTAVAGLDEVQSDAFLLMWHSTESPLDPSLREKY
VDLHEKN
TLHEARRRQRRSTRKLVFDCVNAALMEIAGYGPDTQCQRAIPHNGVSNLPEGAKLILVDQVWT
RMKEWFS
SEVKCLSGDDDEDGNSLVVDGLVMKEVVGKWLQHLRLEIDNVGTEIERELLAELVHESVIELT
GRA

>SITRM3/4 (Soly03g115000)

MAAKLLHSLTEDNQDLQKQIGCMTGILHIFDRQSM LASRRRLIGNSPRRLTSGSSHIGSGTSEKE
YTSTYP
KSPAMESHTNKTQDKQRLSTESSRPSFSSSSRSSSFSSLDCNKTSQQEPLAFDRLSFAETPS
REPAAGQ
PNASPQFGRQSLDIRDVVKDSMNREAQRFSAGPAVKEEVAESMSKPGDSPRPVQTLKNFDGA
YDSGPNGK
QNSSVDLKESLRVLAKLREAPWYSSEHRELTRLSYHSKDTSTLSVSKDAPRFSYDGRETNHV
PFEQRDI
SKSTLKLKELPRLSLDSRVSPVRS LNSEPKSNFSSKSMQKDSGNTNAKSPTLQQTSGTPARPP
SVVAKLM
GLDTLPGSMSSTDNKMGLSTSSQVEAPVSFPRSSEVSDPCKPIRTSNTSKNLWKEPTSPKWR
NPDMMAMP
ISRFPIEPAPWKQPDRTRVYEKPISRRTTKTPVKPAHPFSPVYSEIEKRWKDLEFTHSGKDLRALK
QILEA
MQAKGLLETEKEEQDSNFTGQKEHHQKFASPAQSAKLANQRMQRQTDQVTAPT KRGINSSRNF
ESPIVIMK
PAKLVEKSDIPSSSMIPLHGGDSVSRKGNVSRAAKEHQPR TSHGNSPVNPNEARRTSKPPQI
STRSQQL
PKEIISGSIKSSGISPRLQQNKLELEKSRPPTPPSDSNRSRRQSNKQHT EASSPGGRRRPRI
SNIQQH
DDHVSEISSESRNLSCHGNKISGQSNGNVVAESKVD FEVTSFERSLEMTSSPSSSIDASSYLRC
DLVEKK
SIRVLSDEMLTEPAPEYPSVSVLDNAVYMD ESPSPVKHTPKVMKDESCNTADKFSSPPQCD
RSNTLAI
DATSSGLSSEINRKKLQNIENLVEKLRR LNSSHDEARTDYIASLCENTNPDHRYISEILLASGLLL
RDLG
SSLTSFQFHPSGHPINPELFLVLEQTKASTLLKEELCNDKMRQSNPK EKIRRKLI FDVVNESLAG
KLMLV

GPSYEPWLMSQKLAKSTLNAQRLLRDLCSEIEQLQAKPSKCNMEDEEDEWKNILLDDVVHRSE
SWTIFTG
EISSVLDVERMIFKDLVDEIVRGDGSGLRAKPTRRRRQLFAK

>SITRM26a(Solyc02g082680)

MRSLLDLIDFDQGGMARKFLSQKRHGGVDTPRNSLELPVEASQWFYAGGDKAQCAYQMIDW
QEKNCYGYE
APMKKLISEEIARRPNTGYNAPSVVARLMGVDTLPLDTRPLPKHVEKKNEMKDGNSKEEWLR
KVSIDHA
TQSSRQKISIPFNHDESCDSRQIDSRKPNKYKPREHPQEEELQFKKDFEAWQAARFKECSK
FVEHGTS
PSQWLAQQSLNKEKLTLYANSMRTAASEKPTELRGHTVAVNPWERGLLKHQKNINEFPAPAQ
NKTYCVKE
VIPNPDFQNHPLTNSYRRPDVAPAPTKIVILRPGPERIVTNENSWASSPGISEDGRSIEEFLEEV
KERLN
CELQGTNSKRSITVRGGGIETPYSERSPDAKQIAQSIKHAHVTRDFGTTLSRSESTRSYKS
DIHSNG
ESSPEFVNRDTRKFLTERFRNVLKQETSHGVHRLARGSSRSMELNNETCSSEEMRYTSNTGD
KATNLDNM
KGELNMHNRSFRRDHGNDMLEQELSPRSLIRSLAPVSATSFGLLLEDRHMLTGAHIRRQHE
AIEKVTM
NVKKRQKEKFNLRKVSSFSYSFILKGLFGRKVHSWEEPHGQTYNLMKDFPSPPTGTPNFYE
RHENPTE
VPPSPASVCSSINEEYWRQTDYLPSTTSDVPALDDSEMPRVFRDISSNLNELRRQLNQLD
DSEETMI
DEQAVEEEMLEIEDQAEAYIRELLIASGLYDGSRDYISRWDPLGKPISNQVFEEVEESYKQLTK
DEEGY
IKDQLQKINHKLCDMLNEALPSILGVPSTMSRFMKHAVGPMRPPQGGKLLERAWAIVGVYVH
PPWDRA
FQSLDNIVARDLSSTPWSGLIDEDVNALGKDMECQIIGDLIQEMIKDMLS

>SITRM17/20b(Solyc09g063080)

MPMKMLIAQEMSKEVGS GHNPPSVVAKLMGLDAFPQKSVPAIRNHFGGHSRCHTDSSFSYCO
EENESLTE
ELQQELHQYPEQNEYKDVYEVWRHPPKMNSVRSESPQKARHDDQISFEKKSFAVRQKFIEAK
CLSIDEQL
RQSKEFQDALDVLSSNTDLFLKFLQEPNPMFTQHLSNLQSIPPPETKRITVLRPSKMIDDCKFS
GSVKK
NEKDISRAIHIVQGNKAKSHMTFSPPIANWNIHENHAQPTRIVVLKPSLGKTHNFIDASSSPSASP
RVSQ
TETSFVHMEVDEAQESREVAKAITQHMRVNIGGHQRDETLLSSEFANGYIGDESSFNKSEKQY
AAGNVSD
SEVMSPASRHSWEYINRFGSPYSCSSLSRASYSHESSVSREAKKRLSERWAMVASNGSCQE
QRQMRRSNS
STLGEMLALSDIKTTRSIEQDNIKEDPQISNSNSPSNSKDDEGNHKSPKNLLRSMSVPVSSTAFS
SQLNV
GAPETVTGENDLSKHHTTKSRSTKSSLKGFNSLFFSRAKKPNKDRAKCLQSNDDLHSGPKPLR
SLSEIDK
YSGQFLDDPGAECRSTNLRESSCALTCEDLVEKQTTISPEVVFSGSRVCARYLCENQDQPS
ISVLETP

FEEDDHLACISSGGIKPDRHGAELSVHSLRSNLIDKSPPIGSIARTLSWDDTCADTASSVCVRPS
SSTQR
TEEVEREWFSFVQTLTAVAGLDEVQPDFASTMWQWHSPESPLDPSLREKYIDLNEKETLHESK
RRQRRST
QKLVFDCVNAALLEIAEYGADNFQKAIPYMGVHNNLPQGTTTLVLEQVWDWMKEWFSSEM
YLSTDGGD
LNSLVVEEMVGKEVMGKMWLGNLRIELDNVGVVEIEEKLEELVNESVVELTGKM

>SITRM13/14/15/33a(Solyc01g094640)

MAKRSHRHALRYEKDRAGCIWGLISIFDFRHGRATRKLSDRARGSKPVLGSASSSSMQEIPN
PSDDRLN
IEDDEESEVAVPDPRTSVKELMEEEMVNEQSLKDQCNGSEIDTEDVDSQKSWRSRKNRTR
RAFSRPSN
TLSHDLDDAGNLRSEAPCHQDSGGTALDDLDIVMEELRQIHQKNRKFVKLRQGSHNAHNNQS
DQTHPVVE
EKVNAAIEVFINQRSRNNKQLGEDNKTLQSKEFMDALQTLSSNKDLIMRLLQDPNSRLVKQIGS
LEDAQF
EEKQRPNLISESNMSEENRVHAKTDDVINHKQRKFFRRRSKSKQEVYPPMGNETPRSSSKIVILK
PGPTGL
QSPSAQINVNTPARSRYTEKHTIQNERNTSQFSFTEIKRKLKHAMGKDRHGISPEGTIRRFPS
QLKRCN
SDRGVFGENLGWSSPNRDHFYTEKFAKSPLGMKSGDKIVKSKGVEAVTLTGTSDVPRPEMSNI
YIEAKKH
LVEMLDNEDETTEASSGHLSKSLGRILSFPEYNSSPGCSPRNNKDGMLPFQVRKPLTDSIQV
ETDDRLO
HVREDHVTGPSPSSQDLEIESSCSKYPNESTKSASTNLDVPCENGNTMDEIAASTGHTSPEG
DLTEEI
KTRCQVEGEILSVPIDREIQIDGATNAVDDGNSPHVFEVSFDCLKEHPSGKDQNSLSSSPASP
AESSL
VKVEDPDSAVDRKERPSPISVLEPLFLEDDVSPASTICRPVQLHTVDPEIQPRKIHFEFPVSSISE
QDCP
IVCFENEESAFEYVEAVLLGSGLSWDEFLLRWLSSDQILDPSLFDEVELFSSRSCHDQKLLFDC
ANEVLK
AVCERYFGCNPRVSLGKHNIKRPVPGMDLINEVWEGVEWYLLQYSAPHSLEQLVKKDMERSG
TWMNLRLD
LGHIGVEMGEIILEELMDDTILSISGDTLECAEDVLFVPTSETESSVDQ

>SITRM30/34a(Solyc07g032710)

MPPDSLRSVYRSFITCDDPKGVVECSTIRKSHMEKNTPCSSHKDEGRQTVNHTSSFHLMEVS
REQKLN
QVIDSWSKGMTIERHSNDIAKDLLKGALELQESLVMLGKLQHIKLLKKYKHELDGIPIQRTKSE
RISEH
RLNRFEFQKPRFSVDGDCFDELREVIRDNFARQPNSALQFQTNSEKASVGTRIKSSHVPSTSS
SHSSIVQ
SQQVSPPLDGPNIARLMGLEEIPSKSQHQTTTHKVVKQMRPIFEIDLPAKAKPTFISHKVPKPK
TFDEI
IETMYFKGLLRKSTHKFVDSPPVIMKPLYEQNPSSDRNKCEEISPDDHKGASIRYRKTQAGKDH
NNRFS
KERGEAPSKSKTLQVLIQPNTKIIASSPGKHRGEANAKSKTLDFVSQEKQHKNIRASSPGKDL
GEAPAN

SKTLKLLLQEKYPNAMIKASSHRKYLGDATVKVFIQEKQPNTTRASSPEKTPQTKKEPIGKRE
DGTQRV
APAIRNSKEMKNAKIDDSAKFQDQSKMSTLKVVRKPERKPLAAQAKSTIYDLKRITTTASHNSIKR
KKNVK
ANKPIKSTPIATVADIKHKDESKEMVQAEDKDTDRAITNVTSSEELQLEKRANIFEDLVTDNAVN
GENVP
CESSVLSTYCLGDIKLVQINCINLDFTEVNFVNSGATTRYLLLSSESFLCQSKELFETDVWEP
TVWQT
TSVDHEIADSTLLLDCANELLENKRSQCALAVNPLSMKAIKMRKFYVSFEKLVKEICDGIEVLRS
YNKVA
GKNLSADALYPLLERDLWCKGVAGSAWDLAWRTGLTKNEVEQVLNDIEKYLLAAFIDLLTDF
ML

>SITRM25(Solyc03g006840)

MGREWLYWGSQSGKSSSRRTKGEEQVMNNIINDEAAAPSPAGCMCFQIFDLPHFQVALNQ
QSRSLKQHH
HHPSTFFQHHKDPSSLKGVAPRNSLELDEAVPERKSVSSSLSSSSTMKVDEQNLNIPVGIQIRT
SCDSRS
PRVSTSGSRTRTDYGISSECSSSPAGTKTPTLVARLMGLDLLPENNSPRISISTHCNTKSQS
KNVLVN
NNSKNNRRRFSSFESSDIATGTLSPETPRISLARRSDVDHHRHQHRLSLQINKENMGDA
FEFSDSS
STAKMGRNSRRSFHQQENDNQTRSPGYARQIVKQVKESVSSRKVGHDTNTSSSIRRKDNQ
LAATYDQV
VLLKPKKPSNGNDDDFPSSKQTPSCSPRFRFLEPKSTSAKHQTSHPKFSPLSPLSETTTLSL
PAKIVT
KPKPQSSPKVQVQQRKCDKFVPPKPPQACDAIRSKKEELFVRSAAATNKANFSEKKCKLKTPL
SNQLVNT
STVPTILPLKKDPSPPTTKLLIKSQESDTYPSKRRSSSSSRELSSSSSHNSYYYKLTTLQENRD
KCNGA
ISIDGLNFHHQYIQRILKRTGLDKSSPISLAKWYSPSHPLDPSIFHYLELFNSTTHNSTLRSNRKLI
FHL
VDELLVDILIKNNNLKHRSMNGEGLIDALCSKIQDFPSANCQVLEDIDALIERDMKIGGSVFFEEE
VESI
VCEIEREIMEEVLHDDGAV

>SITRM13/14/15/33b(Solyc08g081160)

MEKKRSSRNPHQIDKSQLNCMWGLISSLYFGQNQRKQKLLSNGKGSTKNVIGKNSRKIDALTY
CSDQLYG
YEDGAEVEALGVRTGDKRIKTSIHHEISGEMQKSTQIIARNEQHEEVDYGLFDHMISKYKPSPKK
GCKNQ
SPVYDWKDTETGDIQQASSAEMSIHKLKLASILEAIGSQIHREDGDSKRSSIKNDQLDEISLQVL
QTS
KAFIDQMFIDRKYISKGNMSYEPEQFSNALEMLNSNGDLFLKLLQDPNSLLAKQIRNMQNVQMA
RDSIKS
FMSNRLPDCNISKSEHKHHQSAFEESSNSRPSNKIVLKPPIRTRVRCSENVYCYCSSIQSHHST
SSKGGN
LQHKNFSLKDIKRKLYAMGEKWKEKHLISVGSTVHKLHSVSDRKNLEVDEGGSSCLTTARST
NSFTESN
NKNEAQNKQISTSEAPKVSFLTEKVRKKLDASISYTKKRELDISMEAKRHLSQRLNFVNTTDEA
AMSTQ

PSRTLERILSSPEHDRLFNYCSKQDRKSNPEQPCYNDTSIAELPRDPTHTSFQSPQRHKDSQH
LKSSMLA
SPSEVWSPGSSTDVSSTSPYSMYKLRGVDSIMDRGDHPSPVSVLEPVFTDDLISPSRNEPSGT
VLQPRRI
NFEGCLNKESTENAILNRAEPDLRTYIQSSLHTLHLNWEELWLNRLHLSEQMLDAMLSDELETL
ALQCHS
EPKLLMDYTNALLEAYDSHFYPPWLSFFQPKLWSFPPEKHILLEKVMNEVKQHLVPLMDQPT
LNDHVET
DLAKSGSWLDIRDDTEDVLTQITDDVLEESIMCTVLQLQNFLV

>SITRM30/34b (Solyc12g007140)

MLGKLQEASEYVTGLRKRES DATGVGKTKSERLVADHRYNNNKDEFGKSSLSVDRSRDCYDE
LREVIRDS
LARQNLLPPCCASEKARSGRRKIDLYQDFPSTSFTSLSETSMEKACVADARKLVMSPPELSTSS
SQFASF
DCSRDKEKPKVPNLIARLMGLEEIPSTPLHQKQLEKDMIFKPTRPIFEIDLPAKAKLSVINQKADP
KRRT
LDGIIETMQFKGLLRCKSNNVISHQLKSSAADAPPVIMRPVYAPEVQAERFSTSIRDENPLDTKN
SFGK
RNLKEESAPVNFTVHRKMHTRNIQKSSCIPEKGSKDHNEETLSLTKNRASSPGRTKQPKKEVID
KRVERT
QRAPGAKRSGEMKNVSPNNTTKVQDQSKRTTAKVTKPEKKS NVPEKLVASQRSADSKRITAV
VSQNSRNR
KKNVKTDKSVKSSSIVPVVENMEHNCEQDSDITVTNLTSSEPPCEEVAEISKSVVTDNLKNGE
CSATES
TMTLIQCDHNIPLMEHTRYQIRQDSTEKEFLKSRATTRHILLSNESFLSRAEELFDTDAWEPTVW
KTVSV
ENEMPNSTLVLD CANELLENKRSQSALTISKSPVNMSRVSISFDKLLNEICDAIEVLSHTKVDA
NILSV
DTLYALHERDLSCNGVISTTWDLGWRNAFTLDEVEQIVTDIEKHVVNGIIDDALTELT

>SITRM6/7/8b (Solyc01g100290)

MEVEKRTSKGGFLQLFDWNIKSRKCLFSNKSELPDNSKQGKENANGSANLRLQQAHDHSLGS
NSKQNYDF
YSASSVAEDES YGQKAPGVVARLMGLDSLPTSKE SDPNFNASSDCHSFRDSPYLSFIADFQNE
HHMIVDG
NMRNKLDGFKRNPVEVRLQKVQSRPIERFQSEVLPPKSAKPIAVTQPRLLSPIKSPGFIPKNA
YIIEA
AAKIYQQSPRPAAREKVQSSGSSSAPLRIRDRLRDQIEAVQRQSSIYEAPHRPKEQNSVKNVRR
QPCERGQ
VQSDNLRQLRVSEVSRRDVSQNKGKEKSVSLAVQA KTNVQKREGKESTSSKNPLNQKEQNES
KSGRRRTS
VKVGERKNSLNRPSDVL RQNNQKQNSASNKDGESSNTSAPYHKEKKSSTGNMSRSTKTVS
RIVVNTTAA
TGIASIVETDVGKDLSSSRDSRVSFTGKKQPVNVDIGSDECGADNMMKNKDERSIKCNLTIEG
CSNWET
ADRKNGSDVVSFTFTSPIKKSMPGPTSSSHVLEKNSALCLFPGSYDDQSDSRTSTMP SFRIGG
DDL GILL
EQKIKELTSKVGPSCEDFIKTGTASTSTNAFEDSVSIVAHGRRPQVDLLNEKAGDPGHSSVDDL
QLTATQ

MWQGPNRVENPKTASSITCEGEFSLASSMEPSISGGSCSSLDSFRSLATDGSKYHLSDGSHY
MMNWKTYM
RTHLVEGDAELLDSASSASLADAGEKESTTTLTSSNFNESAYWEFQYIRDIIRSSDMVMEEFLL
GEVQSI
IALDLFDKLENQQARTNKNAEEQLKMRRRVLFHSAVECLELRCKLSFGRGVEAWAKWTTLVQR
KEWLAEE
VYRVIASWTSMEELMVDEVVDKDMSTQDGKWTFDFEACEEGVDIEKEILSSLMDDLIGDLM

>SITRM26b (Solyc03g032110)

MTNDWPEKKNKYVKEVPMKKLISEELAKRPNTGQNVPSVVARLMGLDTLSVDEESLREVSSR
QTVFDSFD
RRSRNSLKFNELKPREHPQEEELQKFKKEFEAYQAAKFKEGSKFVELNTNTVLYANSTRKMVT
ERFIDLK
GLAATENIHERGISKIQKDKNEFLAAARNKTIRALNVKSGSAPAKIVILRPVSDRTGKNEESWAN
SPRIS
EDGSSMEEFLQEVKGRLKFELQEKSFRKTIEKPSDAKIIAQCIAKQARES VTRDVGTTTHRSKS
MQSDRS
EIQRDEASSPEFTKRDTRRILTERLRNVLSDESSHIDKHDRVSTSV AQHREKSKSEEMRYAP
NEVCHG
DDMKDESDRQCYSRQELSNDVMLDQKLFHRNLVRSLSAPVSRSSFGKLLLEDQDMLTGAHI
RRQHEAIE
EVTNVKKWRKEKFNLKAKVSSFKHSFVLKGLFGRKIQSLEESHGNKQMHMKDLQNTQTVA
SKFYVRQE
NSTEVPPSPASVCSTSNEEFWRQTDNFSPSSSSISDVNPLDDTEIPHVFKEISSNLNGTSKNLC

>SITRM18 (Solyc05g054770)

MEGKQHTPSVIARLMSLDELPPRQHLPVKRRRVLSQNYLQKMASIGLREKSSFSVGLSRGIST
QKHQIVK
DVSAAKLKMRYTNSVTPIKEKHSYLMDFEGTSELLSTKHLRDLQAYKPYCHPVHSAVAKSI
CKMSAK
ATAKEKNLRSLHTLEIGSPKDDIGECSEIHLKINFQLDPNENMPHPSTRVIVVKPSSGKYRKTN
HQSVS
LRHGLQSVVDLKYKKFAEHENGAVHNERPGRAESISDTFLKAEALKLPSSKLFSTQRKDNTLN
FFSKRS
SFSKEVKKQTIEKWKLMNGLQEVETTCRSQNLGEMLATDDLETRPQFLDSKRDSQRFCSSSS
VNTQNSGS
CSKDSLVPNHSAGSRIASGSSEGMIGHKASLYGWCPRQKVAGAEKHSKSMNQKQKDNMEYR
DLNLKETDQ
RSPNSVLEPPFQEEEPYTS AFHGLCSVARQLQFLETNSEETYSEGSEM GVSTDGDSETGSPD
LLQDSENI
LKDFKTADGRDFS YLVDVLDEASLHGINLGMCFETWHSLEY PVNPSVFDLLEK KYGKQTSWLK
SERKLLF
DHINSG LSEILHSFLEIYIMGKSFKRCCSTMRRTDIEEELWRMLVSHENEIRKDL SGKAIGNETK
WLQV
EEEIGSICREIEKYLL EELAAELASH

>SITRM6/7/8a (Solyc01g060410)

MVVEKQGSKSGGYVGGFLQLFDWNAKSRKKLFSSKSDIPELSKQKKRCDGNLPMTRVHLNNE
DDTTAVSS
IKGSSDYSCASSVTDEEYYGIKPAGVVARLMGLDCLPSSTLSEPYSTPFFDSQSLRSAPLSRN
LEYQQN

FQTVYSSNLHEKIEDLGRSSFEPKQQKIISRPIEFQTEILPPKSAKSIPATHYKALSPIKRANSIPP
QN
AAHIMETAARILDAGPQATSKVKSPILIRSSSVPLKYKDLIGRAEASQKVAKIAEASRRPAESNAS
KYLKG
QPMNKSWSGSADIARQKDFSDSDSDFGGGKTGKGSVSLALQAKVNVQKREGLNAGSSRSILV
QKESPSKG
ISNQLFTSQPSTEKNTTHKSSVHNSSSVLRQNNQKQNSIADRGKSPSKQFLSNSQGKRTLSDG
SSFARQR
SSGKMAENSKVSSRRLSREADNKKEEAYSCTKSVSRKKRPSDGDQIYEKNQATGSMSTHKSG
KLIQSGTF
MDREISWGENSKGKGTDIISFSFTTPLARSVPTAEPREVLGKSNEFSTDFRSNNMQLTSDCM
NNLKAPL
GHHNLGGDALSTLLDQKLRELSSVVESSRQKTSNSSSSIFEDLSPSLNGLSKTTMLHVNRNH
DDMEVDD
LVSPCNPFGSSTVPLGITGQHKHQVVEEELSGYGSSEYECRKLFGSRFLSPISVLEQSFLTSC
NSSDTA
ESNNTGACKQSSSVQAKEVFGICSWNKFQSMPEVDLLDSASSTFGKEEERKSPNWELEYVK
EIVYNIES
MFMDFTMGRCQKIINPHLFDQLERINIHRHDELKQRRKVVFDVGECLDLRCKQFVEGGYDSW
SKGVLVV
KNKKRLAEEVYREISGWSGMGNYMDELVDKDMSSGFGRWMNFEVEAFELGIQIEKRLNLSL
DEVVADI
LLL

>SITRM9 (Solyc01g091830.2.1)

MASSSPSPLARLSLERRPKLLKEFLLQDDPYSSNDFGSYPNKYIHGSTIIRSNGSSHQLLRSR
SRAAT
ATISAINKVISIVKFLPFTSVKSPSIFPRNISRKLSRKNNYKKSQKHNVDDQVSVKVKVDILRWK
SFRD
LAEKSTPLDSSSPYRYGTITAMTTTTTITGKRTSWCSDSTAEDLPSWWGENGELLGRKNS
VGGYCME
TTKSIINKEELCFDENEQHSPVSILESPFQEDDDEGSMASFQKRKSMMLHRIQQFESLAEENIN
SKVEE
ELKEDEEIEEKAKQLLINCENYMDDDQLLFDFFWNEELITSGKKHQNNVSNVDEKLLREAKSWI
NDYNE
EFEWEIEDKREAYIKDMEKVANWNKFEEEEKQEFILDLEFEVFNLDLVNEVLVDVFSHN

>SITRM22 (Solyc02g086130)

MNDSLAITASSLAITEKKPQRPGGCVGIFFQLFDWNRFFAKKKLFPKLLSPARLKQASKKFGG
DEKQPK
HRLIANENSGGFPIAKSNGMSNTRCESKREMKAPSLVARLMGLESM PAGPGSKAKKASASET
GSYVAEKL
DARPGGSDKEDMDCEKAEIKRELRPQKLQKIGVSERRPVSRFSAEALQLRTVLSRPRKHQPKL
TSPVKSP
RNVSGRNASRLIGAATRILEPGLQKSRAKCALTPKYFSPLEDKADLALHHLEVPNPCVDSKTS
EVRASV
PCKNCGYMLHKNKNGTPNGEEHPSSVSSPVSSYSQPSCQGPGRNMLRPLIINSRDQLERVFE
GSSSDANA
EIDDVSYCAELILGKRPIRSRIAMHGACQGSNVKKDASSVTHVLNQQKQNTSQNRERGMKS
KQSSLQS

NRVLAAAESTINTKSFVAQNRRLGASTRLRMPATADGCKFETERKPYSRRSDSLSPVRKKRLM
NVSQRQE
SSSFVNANLGRESSPYSDKTSRKDVFPISVNSHSTKPKLPCLRESGATNNSSEGSNVVSFTF
RSAMKQK
AGIHAEVTKRKSQNSSSFDATPGRSFFTGNDETAQLQSFPLKGDILGALLEQKLKELTSEEEF
AEGDAA
PRKSTATILQELITALNDETQFHLDLPSKPNRKEDLYDDREVSSRNTSMNFQAIPDSATDLVGN
SLDND
HLSPGCVLEATFSTDSYLS SSPNSSSKDKVLAESVDSIYDEPLFPEPDRDLSDCATSLFTRRSC
RALITD
HVNNISGVLKINQLKGSKLG YANEVILNTEILIGTSPEQQALPVDDGLSVSHFLLNELEMLSSLL
WMTF
GQLLGCNDPKQMNQLKGF AFDCLLEYLDSKFGRYSDSGFRIWSKLPSSMTKEILIADIIIEVKE
WTEFVG
LIPDELIEWDMSHSLGKWTDFEIEEFECGTEVDRHILQVLVDEVVLDLYSSS

>SITRM1/2/3/4/5 (Solyc02g089050)

MSARMLSSITEDNKDLHKKIGCMNGLFQLFDRHHFLIGKHLHGQNHKRLLTGVTDKMETKCTM
QLATEKT
PRDVARNKVESKANPKVEQSKKPQEEQPLCGQRNLPESPSKTL SYKQPSSPSHSGRQSPDF
RDVVKDSM
HREARSLSVKTVTKVEGKLHVMKHIDSPRPFQQPNCGKPSDGTRNVTAKFRDAPRNSKDDLK
HAPRDHPR
FSYDERDSREAMRSSIRLKDLPRLSLDSREQSFRSSASESRNFLGDHKRSSSVVAKLMGLE
ALPNSIP
SNEVDTVIPKSFSTNNSVSVSIKTAEKSKNNQVTRFSQINEKDFGSPRMKSTNSIMRAASTSRL
PLEPAP
WRQPEACRTPKSSARNTDVELSIQSPKLSSSVYGEMEKRITELEFRKSGKDLRALKQILEAMQ
KTRARL
DVQTEELADSDANLEIVQKRQQCNLLSPTIKGTRPPKREDTADKKTWKDVT PRAKNIRDSGWL
LPSPDRK
TKEGTSRAVQNPTLRQQKEGSYPAIGRSSGTASPRPLQKKKQSCPTTTSPEFSRVRRQSIKQS
KESGSSK
RRLQAKPNNLLRVDEESSEISSSTRNFSEQSDAASLQSESNNSLSSHAEGEVTSRNHCVRVNA
KRLEDSK
DKSDILRLNEDRTMAELAISTIEQPSPVSVLDATFYEEDSPSPVKKKTTAFRVEDATDELWYLEY
QDHSP
YSKRIDLGTEATTQKKLEHIKDLVNQLRLLDSSYGASTDQFGSLSQNHNPDRHYITKILLASGLL
KDVDS
VSMAIQLHSSGHLIDQKLFHILEQTEERVIPATEHSKTSARIEFNQKMHRKNVFDTVDEILACKLA
SESC
LMQQGDHLSAQQQLQKEVQSDIDLLNAKKVGM DSEEDDLISILNADLRHQSEDWTNGDSEIPSLI
LDVERL
IYKDLITEIISDEAREQQIRTKRHRQLFTN

>SITRM30 (Solyc04g080270)

MFSPKKTLLHSKTEGKIMSGKSDF AQKLLHDLKLRKERVAAAQSSGYSYSTTRDARANSQT
RGSRQTK
TLESVNSKVGSTSNRSFRFEDSSGQIVTYGTGRVRTSEKVGDL SMALAFAIENGGKFTKMDSG
SSRNPVL

TFLHQFSQRSMDISKDRRTYHIPNSQFPSVSQVHINEVSKGIQKLNQILKACSNGLNFDNRNSIE
VGQDL
LKGAMDLEESLRMLVNLQEASDHMIKPNKNRITLLDEDEDEDAKIVDQKQLDLPRFSFDKPSK
NSYVAK
GIGKNDIKQRLMALSYPDQTPKLHEKQPLSRNKSMHRSASCAPDFRNLDQKNQLKGTKSG
SEKGRISN
VIAKLMGLDELDPQKQDNKASRKGSDPKKKQEPVLMRSAGFIGTRDAENRSSLNVDKNMISDILP
VQDAKF
MRKAEITRASPSRNNMDSSGRVQQQEERSIAVNKDTGTVPSGLPMINNMMDKPHSKNIQLN
QFNFQQKQ
KEQNQTSVKGKIIKTVEIKETISQTKKLQTSRVPPIDIVLQEDIIQKETDKFPLSNEKKALAKDEVH
HMQ
KLLKSEGQDEKHQAGKKEKLPSNKTMQARTHKANQVETISSPKSRSSAASLKKKQSSRNQSIL
GTKNPTK
SKNGAPAKDSSNGINQALAKHRNSSTFVGMQSSSENKNTDQNVLSKEVLSRSEKLNNSQSSKQ
EKPVNLP
STDRMDHHNKIHRRTETSPKIDELSPTLQDTELQKDDKSCSGGAEQSTESQTREANADNIGSNE
PDVSMEI
LDFQTELLGKIENSTSCNIMEKECDNLTDSTVISNENHQEKPQVEISMDQKVREDRPKILQ
ATDQF
NGIHQEASQNSKLFYDEQNKSFPAKFTGKGGIKISNVVRNDQETALTLVVQEPLTVPEKHFKET
VIKNQL
FLNTAEALFKLNIPISILHASDQNNQGEDVKLMIDCGYEIMKRKAIRQELAVHPYATISIGYTKTRS
LDN
LIKQLCNDFDTLKSYGGNEHMSDERDEADYLHNMIGKDMSNRNPDVNSMWDSGWSTEQIMF
SFLEKDDVV
KDVEKHLLNGLINEITMDLLRAISV

>SITRM16/32a (Solyc06g076130.2.1)

MGKNKWSRHVDHEDEDIHPGCMGFIHALGYNSWHSRVKRKSLPRINDGSSHIRSIYSSKGKL
VGQDPSELEMLLDNESHFLVDKGRKSKGSKSLKAKIKDLIAEEMHKEKKKSKKKKSGSS
DQPKFQTSGSVEHSDKKHPSVLVPANVEGGESPDKKRMNAIDAYDTSNDKNALNSQLKDHAE
LLEILRESEAEYQNL SRGQLASYKKARLTKSGSYPVSRKTNFKPIKLEDKKKEVWSSAKGERLI
GVTRTRSLSNYAKTLFTSLGLLDDDGRNLKLDKSSSLSTKGAVDNKENNEELVDVEDVNKVDT
DHQNKSNCCCEIDGFDISENTIIHKRSSSLNEFMNRYTKLFEHSFKKEMNLYPSKSLKLTSEYEI
PPSMSFRIRLSYSESCSLLPNGVSGDIRFSEWLKTVVEERNSHMRGEIEKEEKSIYSTEETG
CKIEQIEGSEDINIDEADNEVVEELSEIIDEVKVFNGNSYDEQEIKCNESIPSDVVPNSEICFKEDI
SNYAEFQISEGFAHKQNVVDILAKADHDKSYRKENADFFYVRDVLHDHSDFSRNFFKTTWYS
EAQVLNPSLVKELESLEWHEEEEECCCLGEFDFCCHHLLFDLVNEVLLQMYDRSFTYYPKALTY
NCRVPQLLENRMNEEVCNNVGTLLRLKPEQESIDTIVDQDLKMDDGWMNLQLESACLALALELED
MIFNDLLEELRCF

>SITRM10/11 (Solyc08g080280.2.1)

MDSKLMKPLPKTLMLKDYLLDDLSSCSSSGFRSYPRRQCCTTVRFLLEIDLKNKYQPALPPPPY
KNKPILRSKQSPPSAKVSAFHKASVAVINAVKHLPFAGARSSSTLKKKKPMMRTIFPRSISRKLK
RSFWKRGDHKEIYWWTAFNRLDKEELKSPVLSPPVIGKITGDSNSSTTTVSKSKCNSNTWSSD
SDYTASTDNSLQTSSGNSEVNSSETVNDVASKKFGTENVTCSSKKGATTGDDSSDSTISSHG
STTNSPNTKKPWPNEEKEQFSPVSTLDCPFDEDEVSSPFQHRLSRVEGTTTTKLMKKIKRFE
CLTELEPLNLDKRIASSESESESEPLNNSSETEEDKQTVEDMVQELKASMPYSYSLKFTTEKLLFD
FFKERILNGDDELKNKLLLESALEWINGKPIDVLLDWKVQENRMAYIRAIENRGEWKNTELEKQQ
VILELEVEIFGSLMNEVLVDVMLS

>SITRM31 (Solyc09g005570.2.1)

MAKNPKDTSSTKCFSSIFQRLICGGSLPHTPCDQFKEANTTTYEANSNKLVGGANSSPGIVARL
MGLESLPREEKSKFGSFSRSKANSGLDYLMQFDLTQQFHRRVRTSLSFREIPNQEESKSEYL
VFCINDEKQEMMKPKKKRQNVEKKQVSGKQNRIGNNKVKKQVIKFEDYPTKMCVESKKNKRK
SKCVVSTKIQLYNNSTPNHLQDDATIPSEGKIQVNSDAMKSKVEKQKEISKEKDHYIKVVGEI
CRLTEEELNESHWITSIRNGENINFEDLCQQFGQQLLQLLIDQLVHELVIFAQ

>SITRM27/28a (Solyc09g009220.2.1)

MAQKHLHELLQEDQEPFLKHAIADRRRCQLNKNPSKYSLQTVKKQKSISSPSNTSTLLCKHACF
FTSIRKKSDDGGSSERLSPINFPAKTKSPVRKVFLHIPASTSSLLLESAMRIQKKQKNRPKLLKKTQ
MGFGLFGSILKFKMKNKREIGMKRNEIVAELTSGSCSCNHSRLSSAGWSESNEEKSMDFETSS
SCRSENEEIEDIELGICENKYCSPISPFSLQKCPSSSTGCRTPDFSSPVASVVRHKTEDKENY
EDLSNIEQEEDEKEQCSPVSVLDPPFDDGHEREYEYEDDEDEEYDDCGIDCNALVQRAQ
QQLLSKLRREFEKLAELEKLEMLLEEEEEEGNNDLEYDNDLSLSYRDRDFETFASEVTFFPD
MKRLVSDLIYEKTTETNNSNREEEVVFGFRVCKRDLDSWQHVRSDTIDMMIESDFKTELDDWKK
FHEQREEAALEVEVSIFRLLVEELAEIIVHFGGHHW

>SITRM16/32b (Solyc09g010790.1.1)

MGKHQDPSISPESPPGCMWILHRKRLPRKRKGGGKRVAVVEDLEDNATATESSPLVATLCTY
MRAKLTMSSTVSFQIVSKIKEPNQVSKSSMLSRIRSLITQEETSKKRKGRHRRSSSCPIQLERTN
SIQHLDLADLQSSHDKTLEHTNYKEMYSVASLLDPPTTKIRDRAVQEPMEVENMRNDSSKMLL
GFIKISIFPSRRSRGRKAVRSRKRHHAKGEDDQSQVGVSEVSGSGGFNSNSVTSTDLSSDDD
VGKNVLIRRAESFDNASACSPRAEKDRESSKLILNRFKNLQKIRYALEESRKERHRIFMDAVL
HKVPHGHRSSKDIKSTFAHCNSPFRSEKMTSFRRTSSVNESLHKYNGFLDSSYREEKHH
ISDRSSFRTSRSPSPGRRSPIGLDRILSMPDLTYNSFKCEDSPERGSSYTLDRATSSSNLYVGI
CKSNEQKSLDIPLGSENHTEKGYNSDSKSTIFLDVSEFDDFGGLKTRENSSPVENIIEGTSSV
SNVDKPIVPLPDMIIQNATSGANELSAAKGAEEEDVVHTDKRGLPSSDLNRLIQVQDKRYECE
NYVKDVLLESGFSGDKIIGKWSADKPVNPSLFDEVEGYCLLDQEGVTCDQLLFDLINEVLLQI
YERSCSYWPKSLTCHTHIHTMPIGYHVLGEVWKDVTLCFESEMKNQPIDDVSRDLAGGET
WMNLQFDAVCGGLELEDLILNDLLEELVFT

>SITRM27/28b (Solyc10g083530.1.1)

MALKHLHELLEEDQEPFYIANKRFDQKPPSKLCKNTCFFSFGESPELRKSPCLLSSPAPAKSP
EIEKFLNVPATTAALLLEAAIRIQKQQSSSKSKTQIKKVKVFGGFGSILKLNKRNNSDKNGEKSFT
CSCINSRVNTEISEEKLMDLNENYGDGSSPLSPFRFLQRCPSSSGELLPGFTSPAASPVYHTK
EDKENYETILGLASIEQLEEEDEKEQCSPVSVLDPPFEEEDERENEDEDEDEDENLDCNYALVQR
AQQQLFCKLRRFEKLAELDPIELEKILLEEEEEEDRAEEEEYQVSNLIFEKIEVKSLNYGEAVFGR
ECKIDLSSQELRSNNIDMMVKSNLKNEFDWNEFKDQREEIAIEFAFSIFGLLVHELGEELIHLA
HS

>SITRM16/32c (Solyc10g084750.1.1)

MGKGLRSRRECNPFGCMFGILHHLNQHRWHQVRKRLPYIKQGGAKHIVAAGDRGSNATAT
DSSNTPEKINVKSEDFPIVVKAIAKTVATQQKSSIKSRLKTLITKELLSSKRVQHRRTLSCPITMP
LEQTAPIRYLGPANVEHSPKIRLNDEILQQPQNKNSVASLLDPPLPEKRKDAVTNNKKCELCAS
MLDMNHLKQCDTKKNGKQPSTNFSFRRTQSLYLREQTKNVSVESKFLDALDLLNMREELFL
KILQDPNSSLARQLQGTRASKGLTKSVSFP SRLSLEKIAARSSNDKSSQDKSQIRGKLLGSAGF
ESAEKLNRLHVARNKEEVTKGVLTRLESFDKLPSSPAALKHHRHNSKLVLARFRNLKEKITHAL
KESRKEKHRIAMDAVLHKVPHGHMSLKNVKPDGSDGFSSESTGNTSRCHSPFSKSKQMSFKR
TSSLNDSLDSYRLLTCFSRDEKQNSSERSLRSRSPSPARSRTIALERILSLPDLRHYSFR
IEETPEASYSETLDTAASTASSNLYSGATRSENEQKSLDIPLGSEKKTQQDSCSDSKILENSLDV

SENSDDIGGLKAEENSFPVEYNMDDNLSTNSTLDPKPISTTLPDMIIQEASTIPADLSAIEGIAENAF
DSNEEEILDHEQMTSLLQIQVDEKNKAEFNYYKDVLNLSGFSGNEFMNLSVFEELGGSFLHQP
ECSGYAEERGNYDQLLLFDLINEVLLQLYERSSLYWPKALTSRSYIHPMLHVGYYLLEEVWKDV
SWWLSYKLENDQSLDDAASRDLDKRDNWMNLQFDAECVGLELEELIFD DLLDELIFIDVY